

ISic0179

I.Sicily inscription 0179

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Provenance not recorded; CIL noted as in the house of the doctor Matthaeus Bertholus in Termini Imerese; not located since

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Described as simply 'marmor candidum' in CIL, with an indication that the lower edge is broken off

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Halaesina

2. vixit ann(is)

2a. []

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285258

EDR 127473

EDCS 22100110

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7408 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 101

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